

Exploring the CLEWs Nexus for Upscaling of Clean Energy in Ghana

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Executive Summary

The transition to clean energy is pivotal to Ghana's sustainable development. This study therefore explores the potential impacts of various energy transition scenarios on Ghana's energy mix, water and land requirements as well as CO₂ emissions through the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) framework from 2020 to 2070. Utilizing the OSeMOSYS platform, three scenarios are analyzed - Baseline, Transition Target 1 (TT 1), and Transition Target 2 (TT 2). The Baseline which examined the current trajectory with low clean energy adoption shows limited progress towards significant CO₂ emission reductions and other resource optimization. The second scenario, TT 1 which aligns with Ghana's net zero targets by 2030 demonstrates significant improvements in emission reductions and resource efficiencies up to 2030. However, emission reduction gains were eroded due to non-upscaling of the RE beyond 2030. Finally, TT 2 which is an accelerated approach with a 20% increase in renewable energy, enhanced nuclear power integration offers the most substantial reductions in CO₂ emissions and optimizes other resource use. The findings highlight the significant role of renewable energy and nuclear power in reducing the reliance on fossil fuels, optimizing other resource utilization, and mitigating environmental impacts. Thus, government should develop and implement integrated resource management policies that reflect the interconnections between land, energy, and water systems. Also, government should prioritize investment in solar, wind, and nuclear technologies to achieve higher renewable energy penetration to achieve cost reduction in energy generation.

Keywords: CLEWs, climate change, energy, land, water systems, OSeMOSYS, Ghana.

1. Introduction

Ghana is committed to enhancing its socio-economic standing by sustainably leveraging its resources in alignment with its developmental agenda over the coming decades. However, this commitment faces significant challenges from population growth, urbanisation, and climate change-induced events such as floods, severe droughts, tidal waves, migration, conflicts, among others. These events can severely impact the country's resource system management.

In response, Ghana aims to build a climate-resilient economy, a goal reflected in its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) (Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2024). Yet, most of Ghana's resource management policies, aligned with the NDCs, are typically implemented in isolation, failing to consider the interconnections among land, energy, and water systems. This siloed approach contrasts with the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) modelling framework, which emphasizes the interdependencies and vulnerabilities of these systems to climate impacts (Howells et al., 2011; Welsch et al., 2014; Ramos et al., 2020).

Against this background, this report aims to examine the effects of scaling up renewable and nuclear energy resources on the interlinkages among land, energy, and water systems within the context of the dual causality of climate change.

The overarching objective is to reduce CO₂ emissions. The primary research questions guiding this study are:

- a) *What strategies and policies can help Ghana achieve its renewable energy goals and carbon reduction?*
- b) *How will the shift to renewable energy affect water usage in Ghana's power sector?*
- c) *What land use changes are anticipated with the upscaling of renewable energy projects?*

Through the systemic-thinking approach (CLEWs) of analysis, this report seeks to provide insights into the challenges and opportunities in Ghana's pursuit of sustainable resource utilization in the face of climate change.

The report is organized into five sections: Introduction in Section 1, Methodology in Section 2, Results and Discussion in Sections 3 and 4, respectively, and Conclusion in Section 5.

2. Methodology

The baseline model utilized the Starter Data Kit (SDK) for Ghana, supplemented with data from the Ghana Energy Commission. The modelling approach considered the interconnections within the country’s resource system under climate change scenarios from 2020 to 2070. The CLEWs framework utilising OSeMOSYS platform was employed. The CLEWs framework integrates assessments of energy, water, and agricultural systems, enabling simultaneous analysis of their interlinkages and their impact and vulnerability to climate change (Howells et al., 2011; Welsch et al., 2012). OSeMOSYS, a bottom-up cost-based linear programming approach, determines the optimal minimum cost of an appropriate CLEWs model in the face of constraints (Howells et al., 2011).

Three scenarios were examined, namely the baseline scenario (also called business as usual), transition target one scenario, and transition target two scenario. The scenario label, description and key assumption of each scenario are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Scenarios and key assumptions

Scenario	Description	Key assumption
Baseline	Reflects the current trajectory with minimal changes, showcasing a mix of conventional and slowly increasing renewable energy sources. Also, there is inclusion of Ghana’s first nuclear by 2031	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical trend in renewable energy (RE) penetration reaching 10% by 2070 • First nuclear plant (1 GW) in 2031
Transition Target 1 (TT 1)	Shows moderate increases in renewable energy and nuclear power, reflecting the Ghana’s net-zero targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10% RE by 2030 • Upscale nuclear to 2 GW by 2040 • Phase out liquid fuel for power generation by 2040
Transition Target 2 (TT 2)	Illustrates a more aggressive shift towards renewable energy and nuclear power, with higher percentages of renewables in the energy mix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upscaling RE to 20% by 2030 • Further upscale nuclear to 3 GW by 2050 • Phase out liquid fuel for power generation by 2040

Figure 1: Ghana CLEWs reference system

3. Results

3.1 Power Generation Capacity

As shown in Figure 2, the Baseline scenario demonstrates a gradual uptake of renewables, specifically wind, solar, and biomass, alongside natural gas thermal plants. The natural gas-fired thermal capacity increases from 3.13 GW in 2020 to 55.37 GW by 2070, indicating a heavy reliance on natural gas for power generation. Nuclear power is introduced in 2031 with a capacity of 1 GW. The scale-up of renewables shows significant growth in Solar PV from 0.10 GW in 2020 to 26.31 GW in 2070, while wind capacity also grows to 9.26 GW by 2070.

Figure 2: Power generation capacity by technology

In comparison, the TT1 scenario sees natural gas-fired thermal plants growing significantly, despite the scale-up of renewables by 2030 and the increase of nuclear power capacity to 2 GW by 2040. Solar PV grows to 4.36 GW by 2030 and then stabilizes.

The TT 2 scenario shows a more moderate increase in natural gas-fired thermal capacity, along with an additional 1 GW of nuclear power, totalling 3 GW by 2050. Solar PV experiences a rapid increase, reaching 52.62 GW by 2070, and wind capacity grows significantly to 18.52 GW by 2070. The upscale of nuclear and renewables (solar, wind, and biomass) displaces a significant amount of thermal plants, reflecting a diversified and balanced energy generation capacity.

3.2 Energy Generation Mix

Like the power generating capacity profile, the Baseline scenario shows the energy generation mix is heavily dominated by thermal power, which accounts for 88% of the total energy generated by 2070 (see Figure 3). This reflects a continued heavy reliance on natural gas-fired power plants. Hydropower contributes a minor share of 2%. Other renewable energy sources, including solar and wind, contribute 10% to the energy mix, showing some growth but still playing a relatively limited role compared to thermal power.

Figure 3: Energy generation

In the TT1 scenario, thermal power's dominance increases even further, making up 97% of the total energy generation by 2070, despite the initial upscale of renewables by 2030. This indicates that as demand evolved and no further significant investment in renewables occurred, there was a need for more natural gas-fired power plants, overshadowing efforts to introduce other forms of energy. Other renewables see a significant reduction, contributing only 1% to the energy mix, indicating minimal uptake of renewable energy technologies in this scenario. By the end of the period, this scenario behaves similarly to the Baseline Scenario.

However, the TT2 scenario presents a more balanced energy generation mix. Thermal power's share decreases to 78%, showing a reduced reliance on natural gas-fired plants compared to the Baseline and TT1 scenarios. The contribution of other renewable energy sources increases substantially to 20%. This significant rise in the share of renewables highlights a stronger adoption and integration of solar and wind energy, reflecting a more diversified and sustainable energy mix for Ghana by 2070.

3.3 Water Requirement

In the Baseline, the power sector emerges as the dominant consumer of water, utilising 90% of the total water resources by the end of the planning period (Figure 4). This heavy reliance on water for cooling in thermal power plants underscores the significant interdependence between energy and water systems. The public water supply accounts for 9% of the total water use, while agriculture uses only 1%. This low water demand from the agricultural sector highlights Ghana's reliance on rainfed

agriculture with little or no irrigation, despite the sector's critical importance for food security.

Figure 4: Sectoral water use requirement

In the TT 1 scenario, the water requirement remains similar to the Baseline Scenario. However, in 2030, there was a temporary decrease in the power sector's water requirement due to a 10% increase in renewable energy capacity for that year. Over the following years, the need for water in the power sector increased significantly as more thermal plants were built and no further substantial investments in renewables were made. This scenario indicates a reprieve in water usage, followed by an intensification of demand.

Conversely, the TT 2 scenario shows a different trend. With the upscale of renewables to 20% and an increase in nuclear capacity to 3 GW, the water requirement for the power sector decreases significantly. This reduction in water demand from the power sector frees more water for public uses, demonstrating a beneficial shift towards a more sustainable and balanced CLEWS nexus. This scenario highlights the positive impact of diversifying the energy mix with more renewables and nuclear power on the overall water resource allocation.

3.4 Land Requirement

The land requirement graph, presented in Figure 5, illustrates the projected land usage across different sectors in Ghana for the Baseline, TT 1, and TT 2 scenarios from 2020 to 2070.

In the Baseline, the requirement of land for agriculture continuously increases, while forest land gradually declines over time. This trend results from the gradual upscale of renewables and nuclear, which require land for infrastructure development. Land for other uses and water remains stable.

Figure 5: Sectoral land use requirement

The TT1 scenario is similar to the Baseline but indicates a moderate increase in land requirement for energy compared to the Baseline, competing with forest land requirements. However, the TT2 scenario, which aggressively increases renewable energy sources, highlights the need for careful land use planning. The expansion of solar and wind farms will require significant areas of land, impacting forest land and existing land use patterns. This shift emphasizes the need for integrated land management strategies that balance energy generation with other land uses, considering the broader CLEWS (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) nexus.

The increase in renewables, while reducing reliance on water-intensive thermal power plants, introduces new challenges in terms of land allocation. Effective land use policies and innovative solutions, such as dual-use approaches where land serves both energy generation and agricultural purposes, will be crucial in managing these changes sustainably.

3.5 CO₂ Emissions

Both Baseline and TT1 scenarios project the power sector's emissions to be 21% of the total CO₂eq emissions by 2070. This indicates that without significant changes in energy production methods, emissions from the power sector remain high. Emissions are slightly reduced to 20% under the TT2 scenario, which involves a higher

penetration of renewable energy (20% by 2030) and further upscaling of nuclear power (3 GW by 2050). This reduction, although modest, reflects the potential impact of increased renewable energy integration and nuclear power on lowering emissions..

Figure 6: Sectoral CO₂ Emissions

4. Discussion

The energy generation mix in the Baseline is dominated by thermal power, accounting for 88% of the total energy generated by 2070, with renewables contributing only 10%. In the TT1 scenario, thermal power's dominance increases to 97%, with renewables contributing a mere 1% by 2070. This indicates a heavy reliance on natural gas, overshadowing the initial efforts to introduce renewable energy. The TT2 scenario, however, presents a more balanced mix, with thermal power's share decreasing to 78% and renewables contributing 20% by 2070. This highlights a stronger adoption of renewable energy technologies, reflecting a more diversified and sustainable energy mix.

The power sector's water requirement in the Baseline reaches 90% of total water resources by 2070, emphasizing the significant interdependence between energy and

water systems. The TT1 scenario shows a temporary decrease in water requirement in 2030 due to an increase in renewable capacity but ultimately mirrors the Baseline with a 90% share for the power sector by 2070. Conversely, the TT2 scenario demonstrates a substantial reduction in water demand for the power sector, accounting for 89% of total water use by 2070. This scenario illustrates the positive impact of increasing renewables and nuclear capacity on reducing water usage in the power sector, freeing water resources for public supply and other uses.

In the Baseline, land requirement for agriculture increases, while forest land declines due to the gradual expansion of renewables. The TT1 scenario shows a moderate increase in land requirement for energy up to 2030. The TT2 scenario emphasizes the need for careful land use planning, as the expansion of solar and wind farms requires significant land areas, potentially affecting forest land and existing land use patterns.

The Baseline results in the highest CO₂ emissions due to the predominant use of natural gas-fired thermal plants. The TT1 scenario shows a similar trend after 2030, with high emissions despite the initial scale-up of renewables. In contrast, the TT2 scenario achieves significant CO₂ emission reductions through the increased adoption of solar, wind, and nuclear energy.

5. Conclusion

The study underscores the importance of upscaling renewable energy and nuclear power to reduce reliance on fossil fuels, optimize water and land use, and achieve significant CO₂ emission reductions. The baseline scenario's slow RE penetration did not reduce CO₂, as this may prevent Ghana from meeting its 2030 CO₂ targets. Slow RE penetration results in marginal CO₂ emission reductions, increased water demand for cooling thermal plants, and more land required for solar and wind installations. Conversely, aggressive RE adoption sharply reduces CO₂ emissions, decreases water demand due to increased use of clean energy (RE and nuclear), and necessitates more land. Key policy recommendations include:

- Develop and implement integrated resource management policies that reflect the interconnections between land, energy, and water systems.
- Prioritize investment in solar, wind, and nuclear technologies to achieve higher renewable energy penetration to achieve cost reduction in energy generation.
- Implementing clean, efficient, and sustainable energy technologies.
- Increasing renewable energy penetration to reduce water requirements for thermal power cooling, thereby freeing water for other uses.
- Adopting integrated land management strategies to balance energy generation with other land uses, considering the broader CLEWS nexus.

Future research should include detailed data on water, land use, and transport to expand the model and work with sectoral stakeholders for further development. This

will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impacts of energy transitions on Ghana's sustainable development.

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